

Farmers responses on climate change to support sustainability of farming system in Lampung Region

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ABSTRACT

Climate change is a natural and an unavoidable phenomenon due to natural degradation. The impact of climate change such as extreme droughts and floods on agriculture occurs in some areas of Lampung Province. It is expected can decrease in rice production and livestock businesses which effect to farming sustainability. Following problem of the effect is farmer response to climate change. The aim of this research was to analyze the responsiveness of farmers-breeders in dealing with climate change in Lampung Province. Research method was carried out by farmers surveying in Tanggamus district, Central Lampung and East Lampung. Research location was determined purposively. The number of respondents was 100 farmers-breeders who were determined randomly. The research was performed in April-September 2017. Data was collected through structured interviews by using questionnaires according to research objectives. The results showed that farmers in Lampung tend to be responsive to climate change. In order to overcome the climate change, the breeders provide food reserves by planting forage crops and optimizing the use of agricultural waste. While rice farmers applied alternative irrigation reserves for the dry season and built drainage channels and collected water in the rainy season. It was important to socialize to the wider community in an integrated manner to support environment sustainability. The community is encouraged to protect the natural environment from potential damage. The government needs to build alternative irrigation sources as water reserves in the dry season as well as water reservoirs as a place to collect the water during rainy season.

Keywords: *farmer-breeder responsiveness, climate change*

INTRODUCTION

In Lampung Province, rice and livestock are superior local commodities. Harvested area of rice is not less than 660,560 ha per year with a production of 3,496,489 tons of milled rice (BPS Provinsi Lampung, 2016). Even in 2017, according to the Department of Food Crops and Horticulture, the rice production reached 2.5 million tons of rice which is equivalent to meet the needs of 9.8 million people in the province. The assumption of rice consumption is 92.4

kg per capita per year so in 2017 there is still a surplus of 1.5 million tons of rice. While the cattle population in 2017 reached 742,775 head, with beef production of 12,336,746 kg. The goat population reaches 1,326,103 head and meat production was about 1,806,760 kg (BPS Provinsi Lampung, 2017).

Increase in rice and livestock production was supported by implementation of agricultural technology innovations such as the use of adaptive rice cultivars (Widodo, 2004), season-adaptive superior varieties of rice (Sumarno, 2006), implementation of integrated crop management of wetland rice (Departemen Pertanian, 2008), implementation of Jarwo Super technology (Badan Litbang Pertanian, 2016), as well as acceleration and encouragement of technology adoption in order to increase farmers knowledge and adoption (Nurasa and Supriadi, 2012; Sembiring et al., 2012).

Climate change is a long-term alteration in term of distribution of weather patterns statistically over a period of time from decades to millions of years. The climate change occurs in certain regions or in all regions of the earth. The climate change affects at least three climatic elements and natural components that are closely related to agriculture, namely rising air temperatures which also affect other climatic elements, especially the humidity and dynamics of the atmosphere, and rising sea levels due to the melting of icebergs in North pole (IPCC, 2007). In general, all forms of agricultural systems are very sensitive to climate variations. The occurrence of delays in the planting or harvest season will have a large impact both directly and indirectly, such as food security, fertilizer industry, transportation and others (Shi et. al., 2016; Gerald et al., 2014; Grimm et al., 2013).

The uncertain climate has an impact on the decline in food production in Indonesia (Kementerian Lingkungan Hidup, 2001). At that time climate change which has an impact on the high intensity of rain in a short period will cause flooding which in turn causes the declining of rice production since the rice fields are submerged in water (Departemen Pertanian, 2003). High rainfall also results in land loss due to soil erosion, resulting in losses suffered by the agricultural sector reaching US \$ 6 billion per year (Asian Development Bank, 1994). The climate change not only causes flooding but also drought. As with floods, drought brings similar losses in the agricultural sector.

The most obvious impact of the climate change on the agricultural sector are the degradation and deterioration of the quality of land and water resources, agricultural infrastructure, decreased production and productivity of food crops, which will result in threats of vulnerability to food security and even poverty. The impact intensity could be reduced if there are policies that can produce incentives for farmers and other actors in the agricultural sector to mitigate and adapt to the climate change as early as possible. Various ways can

be performed because the climate change is in accordance with necessity. The experts summarize into 3 outlines namely anticipation, adaptation and mitigation strategies. In Lampung, the climate change causes droughts and floods which have the potential to reduce rice production by 50-80% and reduce the production of ruminants and goats 15-40%.

Starting from the condition of the superiority of the Lampung region as a producer of food, especially rice and as an area of livestock barns in Indonesia which has high productivity. On the other hand, the occurrence of climate anomalies that are expected to have an impact on the sustainability of the farming carried out by the farmers. As well as the impact on agriculture in Lampung in the form of extreme droughts and floods. It is feared that it will result in a decrease in rice production and a decline in livestock businesses and threaten the sustainability of farming. The problem is to what extent the farmers are responsive to the conditions of the change. Objective of the research is to analyze the responsiveness of farmers in dealing with climate change in Lampung.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This research was performed in April-September 2017 through field observation on wetland and dry land agro-ecosystems. Research locations were determined purposively with consideration as a center of rice production and ruminants (cattle/goats). The locations include (1) the area of Tanggamus Regency covering Kota Agung Timur District (Talangrejo and Tanjung Anom Villages); Gisting District (Campang Village, Gisting Atas and Sidokarto); Sumberejo Subdistrict (Dadapan and Tegal Binangun Villages) as a center of rice and Saburai goat livestock, (2) Central Lampung Regency in Punggur District (Ngesti Rahayu Village) as a center of rice and cattle, and (3) Pekalongan District, East Lampung as rice centers and Ongole cattle.

Data was collected by structured interviews to 100 farmers –breeders by using a list of questions (questionnaires) according to the research objectives. The number of respondent was taken randomly based on the amount of data of farmers in the village selected/sampling frame (Singarimbun and Sofyan, 1989), information was taken from extension agents or livestock service officials. Data analysis was carried out in descriptive statistics (Nazir, 2005). The analysis focus on the responsive analysis (response) of farmers to climate change related to farming conducted by farmers.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Response of Farmers to Climate Change

The results of the farmer response to climate change showed that generally farmers are quite responsive to the existence of climate change related to farming (Table 1).

Table 1. Response of farmers-breeders against change climate in Lampung (%).

No.	Description	Response Scale					Total (%)
		1	2	3	4	5	
1.	Attention of farmers to weather changes that change frequently (%)	6,67	6,67	26,67	60,00	0,00	100
2.	The response of farmers to the occurrence of shifts rain throughout the year (%)	6,67	0,00	33,33	53,33	6,67	100
3.	Farmers respond to extreme heat (%)	6,67	6,67	20,00	60,00	6,67	100
4.	Farmers' attention to extreme cold weather (%)	13,33	13,33	13,33	60,00	0,00	100
5.	Attention of farmers to the explosion of pests and diseases (%)	6,67	6,67	13,33	60,00	13,33	100
6.	Farmers respond to the shift in planting season (%)	6,67	6,67	26,67	53,33	6,67	100
7.	Farmers' knowledge of climate and climate change (%)	6,67	26,67	20,00	46,67	0,00	100
8.	Knowledge of farmers on the consequences of changes in weather and climate for agriculture (%)	20,00	20,00	6,67	53,33	0,00	100

Description: 1 = Very Unresponsive; 2 = Not Responding; 3 = Fair Response; 4 = Response; 5 = Very Responsive

Source: Primary Data Survey of Farmers - Breeders in Lampung (processed in 2017)

The analysis carried out on the response/responsiveness of farmers to climate change consisted of attention of farmers to weather changes, the response of farmers to the occurrence of shifts rain of the year, Farmers respond to the occurrence of weather the extreme heat, the attention of farmers to extreme cold weather, the attention of farmers to the explosion of pests and diseases, the response of farmers to the shift of the planting season, the knowledge of farmers about the changes in weather and climate, knowledge farmers to the consequences of changes in weather and climate for the

agricultural world. This condition is in line with the research of Shi, J., et. al. (2016) that a higher level of knowledge about the causes of climate change is related to increasing concerns that will be responsive to climate change.

Anticipation of Farmers to Climate Change

The indicator of analysis of anticipation on lowland rice farmers to climate change consist of : (a) preparing water pumps for anticipation of drought, (b) renting water pumps for anticipation of drought in rice plants, (c) making *rorak* as water reserves for anticipation of drought in rice plants, (d) making ponds in groups as water reserves for anticipation of drought in rice plants, (e) strategizing in groups as countermeasures for anticipation of dryness, (f) using mulch (waste plant litter) in a nearby location to conserve water use during drought, (g) hold deliberation together to make alternative irrigation water sources in the event of drought in rice plants, (h) make drainage channels at rice planting locations to anticipate floods that will occur, (i) make a barrier/dam building for protect rice plants from the dangers of flooding, (j) deliberate in groups to regulate water control DAM to protect rice plants from the dangers of flooding, (k) create rainwater ponds / reservoirs in rice planting locations to anticipate not flooded, (l) conducting group meetings to solve problems (finding solutions) in the event of a flood that inundates the rice field area, (m) following/ paying for rice planting insurance if there is a risk of crop failure due to drought/*puso*/flood, (n) preparing if at the time of the explosion an attack of pests that attack rice plants, (o) doing *gropyokan* or joint control of the explosion of pest attacks on rice plants. The analysis of anticipation showed in Table 2. The most rice farmers in certain areas tend to be unprepared in anticipating climate change.

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Table 2. Farmer action to climate change in rice field

No.	Description item	Response Scale					Total (%)
		1	2	3	4	5	
1.	Preparing water pumps for anticipation of drought (%)	40,00	6,67	20,00	33,33	0,00	100,00
2.	Renting a water pump for anticipation of drought in rice fields (%)	53,33	6,67	26,67	13,33	0,00	100,00
3.	Make <i>rorak</i> as a water reserve for the purpose of anticipating drought in rice plants (%)	73,33	13,33	13,33	0,00	0,00	100,00
4.	Making ponds in groups as water reserves for anticipating drought in rice plants (%)	80,00	6,67	6,67	6,67	0,00	100,00
5.	Developing strategies in groups as a countermeasure to anticipate drought (%)	33,33	20,00	20,00	20,00	6,67	100,00
6.	Using mulch (waste of plant litter) in a nearby location to save water use during drought (%)	53,33	13,33	20,00	13,33	0,00	100,00
7.	Conducting joint deliberations to make alternative irrigation/water sources in the event of drought in rice plants (%)	40,00	26,67	13,33	20,00	0,00	100,00
8.	Constructing drainage channels at rice fields to anticipate floods (%)	40,00	26,67	20,00	13,33	0,00	100,00
9.	Making barrier buildings/ dams to protect rice plants from the dangers of flooding (%)	53,33	26,67	20,00	0,00	0,00	100,00
10.	Discussing in groups to regulate water control DAM to protect rice plants from the dangers of flooding (%)	60,00	20,00	13,33	6,67	0,00	100,00
11.	Constructing a pool /reservoir / <i>rorak</i> containing rainwater in the rice fields to anticipate not to be flooded (%)	73,33	13,33	13,33	0,00	0,00	100,00
12.	Conducting group meetings to solve problems (finding solutions) in the event of a flood swamping the rice field area (%)	66,67	6,67	0,00	26,67	0,00	100,00
13.	Applying insurance if there is a risk of crop failure due to drought / <i>puso</i> / flood (%)	66,67	6,67	20,00	0,00	6,67	100,00
14.	Preparing yourself when a pest explosion attacks rice plants (%)	0,00	13,33	20,00	46,67	20,00	100,00
15.	Doing <i>gropyokan</i> or joint control of the occurrence of an explosion of pest on rice plants (%)	20,00	6,67	26,67	46,67	0,00	100,00

Description: 1 = Never; 2 = Rarely; 3 = Sometimes; 4 = Often; ; 5 = Very Often

Source: Primary Data Survey of Farmers - Breeders in Lampung (processed in 2017)

Whereas for the actions or anticipations of farmers to climate change

showed that most of farmers tend to prepare themselves in dealing with these conditions (Table 3).

Table 3. Anticipation of farmers to climate change in Lampung (%)

No.	Description item	Response Scale					Total (%)
		1	2	3	4	5	
1.	Preparing fermented feed reserves from materials around the residence (%)	13,33	0,00	33,33	46,67	6,67	100,00
2.	Preparing fermented straw in sufficient quantities to supply feed for livestock during droughts and floods (%)	20,00	6,67	40,00	26,67	6,67	100,00
3.	Preparing specific strategies for raising livestock when there is a shortage of feed (%)	13,33	6,67	20,00	53,33	6,67	100,00
4.	Planting sufficient amounts of grass/hay as a supply for livestock during droughts and floods (%)	6,67	0,00	13,33	60,00	20,00	100,00
5.	Utilizing the types of waste plants around the residence as the main source of animal feed (%)	13,33	6,67	26,67	46,67	6,67	100,00
6.	Conducting routine treatment for livestock to anticipate an attack of pest disease (%)	0,00	20,00	33,33	40,00	6,67	100,00

Description: 1 = Never; 2 = Rarely; 3 = Sometimes; 4 = Often; 5 = Very Often

Source: Primary Data Survey of Farmers - Breeders in Lampung (processed in 2017)

The indicators or items of analysis were emphasized on the actions or anticipation of farmers consist of: (a) prepare fermented feed reserves from materials around the place of residence, (b) prepare fermented straw in sufficient quantities to stock feed for livestock during drought or flood, (c) prepare a special strategy for raising livestock, (d) Plant sufficient forage to supply feed for livestock when there is a shortage of feed in sufficient quantities to stock feed for livestock during droughts and floods, (e) utilize plant waste - plants around the house as the main source of animal feed, (f) carry out routine treatment for livestock to anticipate pests and diseases attack. This condition is in line with the research has been done by Kettle et al., 2014 that increasing the understanding of a person, whether it is farmers, breeders, officers, policy

makers, etc. about the risks and impacts of climate change, will do management actions related to adaptation planning such as climate change.

CONCLUSIONS

Farmers tend to be very responsive to climate change in the Lampung region. In order to anticipate climate change, breeders provide food reserves by planting forage crops and optimizing the use of agricultural waste around their houses that are potentially used as feed. While, the efforts to anticipate climate change by wetland rice farmers by searching and providing alternative irrigation sources for the dry season and building drainage channels in extreme rainy season.

The climate change tends to have a negative impact on the sustainability of farming related to the emergence of pests and diseases explosion, decreasing in food and livestock production, declining in the farmers income, the sustainability of farming in terms of planting rotation, the availability of water resources in the five-year cycle, and extreme drought and flooding at certain times.

It is necessary to continuously disseminate information to farmers and breeders on the impacts of climate change in Lampung by the government and environmental observers. The community is encourage to constantly protect the natural environment from potential damage.

The government needs to make an integrated program in areas efforts to anticipate programs that are real in areas that are often affected by extreme climate change in Lampung. These efforts include procuring and building of alternative irrigation sources as water reserves in the dry season and drainage channels and water reservoirs as a place to harvest water during the rainy season.

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